

Societal & Political Engagement
of Young People in Environmental Issues

D7.9: 3rd Network of Interest

WP7 – Dissemination

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1 *Executive summary*

The Deliverable D7.9 “3rd Network of Interest” provides an update of the Deliverable D7.6 “2nd Network of Interest”. It describes the work carried out from Month 24 (May 2017) until Month 30 (November 2017) with regards to the development and maintenance of the STEP Network of Interest (NoI), as well as all implemented plans for the engagement of the STEP Network of Interest (NoI) members in STEP.

The STEP NoI is a community of individual persons originating from different types of organisations that share a common interest relevant to the STEP objectives. These individuals act as a dissemination pole for other stakeholders, but also have the potential to create a solid customer base for the future commercialisation of the STEP outcomes. The dissemination impact indicator for the STEP NoI is 1,000 registered individual stakeholders by the end of the project (Month 30). This target has been achieved since Month 18 (November 2016) and today there are **2,712 registered individual stakeholders**.

2 Introduction

2.1 Purpose of the deliverable

The deliverable D7.9 3rd Network of Interest represents the 3rd edition of the D 7.4 1st Network of Interest. This deliverable is submitted 30 months after the beginning of the project and seven months after the submission of the second version of the deliverable. The present document intends to provide an update on the actions carried out from Month 24 (May 2017) until Month 30 (November 2017). The purpose of these actions was to further engage existing network members, as well as to enrich the network.

2.2 Structure and contents of the deliverable

The structure of the deliverable is the following:

Chapter 3 includes a definition of what the STEP NoI is, a brief presentation of the methodology and the different types of group categories that form the NoI. This chapter also includes the projected metrics and targets set in the STEP project DoA and Dissemination plan.

Chapter 4 is dedicated exclusively to the analysis of the NoI entries and the graphical representation of the results.

Chapter 5 includes a short discussion on the analysis of the 3rd version of STEP NoI.

Chapter 6 includes a brief description of all the activities performed regarding the NoI.

Chapter 7 includes an overview of the progress achieved in relation to the target metrics.

Chapter 8 provides information on the future activities for the maintenance of the STEP NoI

Chapter 9 briefly presents the conclusions of the present deliverable.

3 STEP Network of Interest

3.1 Definition

The STEP NoI is **a community of individual persons** who are affiliated with a variety of private companies, governmental and non-governmental organisations at a local, regional and national level, and share a common interest related to the STEP project. The idea behind the NoI is to gather potential stakeholders/users of the platform, to exchange information and thoughts on the STEP eParticipation platform and its components, but also to offer these individuals the opportunity to test the STEP eParticipation platform and provide feedback. The most significant objective of the NoI establishment is to **act as a main dissemination pole for other stakeholders**, but also to create the first customer base for the future commercialisation of the STEP platform.

3.2 Methodology of the NoI establishment

The methodology for the establishment and development of STEP's Network of Interest is described in detail in D7.4 1st Network of Interest (Chapter 3.2 Methodology of the NoI establishment). As it is described in the abovementioned document, STEP's NoI is divided in two groups, a) the **Core Group** which consists of stakeholders who are considered to be of particular interest for STEP and b) the **General Group** which includes the rest of the contacts that may have an interest on the project. An additional category was added in the NoI, under the name "**Newsletter subscribers**". This category is comprised only by the "email" variable, since people who are registered in the Newsletter are asked to provide only their email. However, since they decided to register on their own initiative, we suppose that they are stakeholders and potential users of the STEP tool.

3.3 STEP Target network categories

Within D7.9 3rd Network of Interest, we utilise the same principles of segmenting and grouping the NoI members and thus the following categories have been formatted: 1) NGOs/Environmental and Youth Organisations, 2) Public Authorities, 3) SMEs/ Private companies, 4) Existing Platforms, 5) University/Institute/Research Centres and 6) Organisers of relevant events/Miscellaneous. These categories are described in detail at D7.4 1st Network of Interest (Chapter 3.3 STEP Target network categories).

3.4 Data entry

Through the whole series of the "Network of Interest" deliverables, we retain the same format of listing the NoI members in a standard spreadsheet software, as it is described in D7.4 1st Network of Interest (Chapter 3.4 Data entry). The following **column variables** were created to assist effective data entry: 1) **Name**, 2) **Email**, 3) **Organisation**, 4) **Type of Stakeholder**, 5) **Country**, 6) **EU/Non-EU**, 7) **Group Type**. It was decided that this dataset is sufficient for the analysis, so there was no need to include additional categories.

3.5 Targets and Metrics

The establishment and maintenance of the NoI is one of the core dissemination activities of the STEP project. Therefore, significant effort was performed to monitor its progress and effectiveness towards the targets set in the STEP Dissemination Plan. The dissemination impact indicator for the STEP NoI was defined at **1,000 registered individual stakeholders** by the end of the project. The impact indicator was achieved since Month 18 (November 2016). However, given the NoI significant role in the effective dissemination of STEP, the network was continuously enriched and additional members were invited and added until the project completion.

4 Analysis

This chapter is dedicated to the analysis of the list of individuals that constitute the STEP Nol. As of the date that the current deliverable was being written (mid October 2017) the Nol list contains **2,712 individual entries**.

4.1 Group type

From the total entries of the Nol, **151** members belong into the Core Group, **2,422** in the General Group and **139** have been subscribed in STEP's newsletter.

Group Type	Number of Entries
Core	151
General	2,422
Newsletter Subscribers	139
Total	2,712

Figure 1 Number of Nol entries per group category as of end of November

4.2 Country

The variable "Country" includes the country that the organisation is based and is active. The number of entries describes the number of individuals registered in the STEP Nol. The category "Newsletter Subscribers" is not included in this analysis, since there are no such data available.

Country	Number of Entries	%
Albania	50	1.94%
Armenia	39	1.52%
Austria	135	5.25%
Belgium	253	9.83%
Bulgaria	2	0.08%
Croatia	31	1.20%
Cyprus	39	1.52%
Czech Republic	112	4.35%
Denmark	46	1.79%
Estonia	36	1.40%
Finland	83	3.23%
France	19	0.74%
FYROM	49	1.90%
Georgia	13	0.51%
Germany	213	8.28%
Greece	88	3.42%
Hungary	50	1.94%
Iceland	24	0.93%
Ireland	59	2.29%
Italy	129	5.01%
Kenya	1	0.04%
Korea	1	0.04%

Country	Number of Entries	%
Latvia	24	0.93%
Lithuania	114	4.43%
Luxembourg	18	0.70%
Malta	34	1.32%
Moldova	30	1.17%
Netherlands	81	3.15%
Norway	71	2.76%
Poland	42	1.63%
Portugal	96	3.73%
Romania	51	1.98%
Russia	6	0.23%
Serbia	63	2.45%
Slovakia	35	1.36%
Slovenia	20	0.78%
Spain	87	3.38%
Sweden	94	3.65%
Switzerland	72	2.80%
Turkey	6	0.23%
UK	148	5.75%
Ukraine	8	0.31%
USA	1	0.04%
Total	2,573	100%

Figure 2 Nol members per Country

4.3 EU/Non-EU

The variable “EU/Non-EU” indicates whether the organisation of registered individuals is based in a country that is a member of the European Union or not. The category “Newsletter Subscribers” is once more not included in this variable analysis, since there are no available data.

EU/ Non-EU	Number of Entries	%
EU	2140	83%
Non-EU	433	17%
Total	2,573	100

Figure 3 Number of Nol entries per EU or Non-EU countries

4.4 Type of stakeholder

The variable “Type of stakeholder” describes the type of organisations to which the registered individuals are affiliated. The category “Newsletter Subscribers” is not included in this variable analysis, since there are not available data.

Type of Stakeholder	Number of Entries	%
1. NGOs/Environmental and Youth Organisations	802	31.2%
2. Public Authorities	1,552	60.3%
3. SMEs/ Private companies	11	0.4%
4. Existing Platforms	65	2.5%
5. University/Institute/Research Centres	110	4.3%
6. Organisers of relevant events/ Miscellaneous	33	1.3%
Total	2,573	100%

Figure 1: Number of entries per organisation type

5 Discussion

Within this chapter a brief discussion on the results generated from the analysis of the 3rd version of the STEP Nol list is presented. It shall be noted that all partners were involved in the Nol list compilation and the maintenance of the respective contacts and performed their best to identify, locate, engage and involve most of the individual entries of the list. However, even though the initial target of 1.000 members has been achieved early in the project duration, the development of the Nol continued throughout the STEP project duration. All additional contacts that were identified were continuously added to the STEP Nol resulting in an extended “Nol list” size, reaching almost three times the size set in the project plan. Of course, the increasing awareness of the STEP project and the dissemination activities performed assisted significantly in achieving such a large number of contacts.

Regarding the variable “Group type”, the **151** entries of the **Core Group** represented **6%** of the Nol, whereas the **General Group** with **2,422** entries represented the **89%** of the network. The difference that occurs between these two groups can be attributed to the fact that the individuals who have a special interest in the project and the tool and are included in the Core Group are far fewer than the rest of the stakeholders, who have a general interest in the project.

Regarding the variable “Country”, a heterogeneous distribution of entries from **43** different countries is observed. The existence of **253 entries (9,83%) from Belgium** is attributed to the fact that many pan-European organisations have their headquarters there, while the 213 entries (8.28%) in Germany could be associated with country’s high level of e-participation procedures. High rates of participation have also been observed from **UK** with 148 entries (5.75%), **Austria** with 135 entries (5.25%) and **Italy** with 129 entries (5.01%). The fact that two partners of the STEP consortium are based in Germany and UK and that the STEP solution is being pilot tested in Italy, might have positively affected the abovementioned rates in those countries.

Regarding the variable “EU/Non-EU”, the majority of entries (83%) originate from the EU. This is attributed to the fact that STEP is an EU funded project targeting primarily EU audiences but also due to the fact that most project partners come from EU, therefore their stakeholder search is focused on EU. Nevertheless, we witnessed an increase of interest from Non-EU countries of almost **300%** (140 entries were reported in D7.6 2nd Network of Interest and today this number has reached 433). That increase signifies that the interest in e-participatory tools is also present outside EU countries and that Non-EU stakeholders perceive value in STEP.

Finally, regarding the variable “Type of Stakeholder”, **1,552 (60.3%)** entries were from **Public Authority members**, followed by **802 (31.2%)** entries by **NGO/Environmental and Youth organisations**, while the contacts originated from University/Institute/Research Centres, Organisers of relevant events and Existing Platforms had approximately similar levels of representation in the NoI with 4.3%, 1.3 % and 2.5 % respectively. In the previous update of the NoI document (D7.6 2nd Network of Interest), we witnessed the dominance of “NGO/Environmental and Youth Organisations” entries (792 entries with 73,6 %), reflecting the importance of these organisations in youth movement in EU and beyond. Following the formation of the 2nd Update of the NoI (D7.6) we have placed an internal goal to engage more Public Authorities and relevant initiatives in the STEP NoI. Following this intermediate period and by concentrating our efforts we managed to attract a significant and substantial number of Public Authorities to the STEP NoI. From a number of 105 Public Authorities, STEP NoI reached a number of 1,552 Public Authority members. The growing interest of Public Authorities in STEP, can be partly justified by an increasing trend of “e-participation tools” as well as from the witnessed value generated for all participating parties (public authorities, youths and citizens) in the STEP Pilots.

6 Activities performed so far

6.1 Online Activities

Since June 2017 a number of newsletters have been sent to the members of the NoI in order to increase awareness on the STEP Project and the Platform, the EU dialogues, as well as to engage them within significant and fruitful dialogues. More particularly these activities included four online invitations – newsletters that were sent to the members of the NoI in order to inform them about STEP’s activities and the EU pilot. All the members of the NoI were invited to experience the STEP tool and participate in public dialogues related important environmental issues. More specific the members of the NoI were invited to participate in the dialogues below:

- 17 Sustainable Development Goals. Which are more important to you?
- Tackling Climate Change
- Air Quality

Additionally, a newsletter-invitation was sent to the members of the STEP NoI in order to inform them for the end of the project and to invite them to participate in STEP’s final event in Berlin. All these invitations/newsletters have been prepared and sent to the contact list via a professional mass emailing solution (Mailchimp).

6.2 Offline activities

Together with the online activities, the STEP team has participated in a number of events in order to disseminate the project and ensure the dialogue about STEP. These activities were supplementary to the local activities that were performed/organized by STEP local pilots. During the events, the STEP team had the chance to present the project to stakeholders, as well as to network with youth workers, policy makers, software developers, participation experts and other stakeholders. From all activities performed since the beginning of May, below are highlighted the ones that are more relevant to the enrichment of STEP's NoI. These activities are briefly presented below, while they are further analyzed in D.7.8 "3rd Report on Dissemination Activities".

- October 2017, Athens for the Eu Clustering meeting: The overall purpose of the workshop was to connect different EU projects, find potential liaisons and share the experience and the impact expectations
- October 2017, "ICT-enabled open government and public sector innovation through digital solutions" & "Digital Transformation of Public Administrations & Project Cluster Event on Sustainability and Exploitation of Project Results". Two linked events were organized on October 2017 targeting Open Government actions in H2020 in order to foster the exploitation of research and innovation results and the post project continuity from operational and policy stances.
- November 2017, 4th International Conference on Internet Science: The Conference aimed in progressing and investigating on topics of high relevance with Internet's impact on society, governance, and innovation.
- November 2017, EPP Study Visit "Europe's youth as partners for sustainable change". The Step workshop was presented in the session "Amplifying youth voices for a positive European narrative".

7 Overview of the progress towards the expected results

As already presented in Chapter 3.5-Targets and Metrics, the dissemination impact indicator for the STEP NoI was 1.000 registered individual stakeholders by the end of the project (Month 30). This target was achieved by the Month 18 (November 2017), while today there are 2,712 registered individual stakeholders. This could be assessed as very good progress, since the target initially set is surpassed.

8 Future plans

From the very conception of STEP, the establishment of NoI deemed quite important, since it would act as a basic pole for the dissemination of the project's results and activities; so its maintenance is important even after the end of the project. This is a difficult task considering that the resources will be limited and uncertain. However, since there is a critical mass of more than 2,700 members in NoI, the consortium decided to keep the members updated on the STEP activities after the conclusion of the project. At the beginning, this will be achieved mainly through online activities (newsletters and social media accounts). Moreover, since the STEP pilots have officially ended, a newsletter is planned to be sent to all the members

of the Nol in order to present each pilot's case and the "Lessons Learnt from STEP" for each pilot. Additional newsletters will be sent in the following months with information about STEP progress and e-participation.

Apart from that a strategic plan has been developed both for the maintenance and the further enrichment of the STEP Nol. More specifically the STEP partners will:

- **Maintain the Nol through advertising and promotion activities**

As described in D.6.4 "2nd Business Plan", after the end of the project the partners who have an interest plan to commercialise the STEP offering. The Nol is a valuable resource for marketing purposes and therefore they will invest on its maintenance. Based on this, they have included in the Business Plan a cost category that foresees costs for advertising and promotion. A part of these costs will be invested on the maintenance and further engagement of Nol.

- **Keep the network active through the BePart network activities.**

On November 2016, the STEP team participated in #BePart in order to disseminate the STEP solution. Over 40 experts from 10 European countries joined the #BePart Summit. During the event, all participants agreed on creating a sustainable network, and to bundle their knowledge and activities, so as to further promote youth digital participation in Europe. In order to open up spaces for exchange, share good practices, build a website, provide information material on successful e-participation methods and helpful tools, develop trainings, lobby and give advice, etc., it was obvious that a coordinating structure and financial as well as personal resources are needed. Hence, a core group was created (in which the members of the STEP consortium had an active role) and it was decided to apply for EU-funding for a 3-year project, to establish a strategic partnership. All the members of this core group are experienced actors in the field of digital democracy and/or youth work and have significant expertise as software developers, participation experts or youth workers in youth organizations and municipal administrations in and throughout Europe.

Following the event, the core group was in close communication in order to submit an application in "Erasmus+ - Key Action 2 - Capacity Building in the field of youth - EACEA - European Commission" programme on March 2017. However, since the time was quite limited it was not feasible for the core group to prepare and submit the application on time. Committed to the initial goal, the members of the core group kept searching for funding and now are in discussions to submit an application in "Erasmus+ - Key Action 2 - Capacity Building in the field of youth" in March 2018. If the proposal is accepted for funding, the network will gradually evolve into the first umbrella organization in Europe which bundles all expertise, projects, developments and tools in the field. It will become a central hub for all individuals or organizations, who are interested in web-based participation and who seek high-quality information and inspiration. In such a case the STEP Nol will be very useful for the dissemination of the new activities on the topic of e-participation.

- **Capitalize on STEP's previous experience through the deployment of STEP No2**

As already discussed by the STEP partners a project that will further deploy the STEP solution based on the experience gained and the lessons learnt from the STEP project is quite essential. In this framework, the consortium is always alerted seeking a suitable opportunity to submit a proposal based on STEP. In the case where the partners find the suitable call and the proposal is accepted, the STEP Nol will be fully exploited.

9 Conclusions

To conclude, with the submission of the current deliverable in Month 30 (November 2017), the NoI has been established, since the initial goal of 1.000 members has been achieved since Month 18 (November 2016). Today STEP's NoI counts **2,712 members from 43 countries**. The analysis and discussion on the results provided an in-depth view of the dataset. The STEP team has implemented a number of online and offline activities in order to maintain the network, keep its members updated on STEP's news and enrich it with additional stakeholders. Since the STEP NoI consists of important potential stakeholders and potential users, the consortium decided to maintain this network and keep the members updated on STEP's future activities.